

Using Exit Slips to Assess Student Understanding

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Commonly used closure techniques include the teacher summarizing the lesson or quizzing the students on the material taught. These techniques are used to stress the key points of a particular lesson.

The use of exit slips is another strategy that may be incorporated to facilitate closure of the lesson. Exit slips are written student responses to questions teachers pose at the end of a class or lesson. These quick, informal assessments enable teachers to quickly assess students' understanding of the material. It takes about 5 minutes to facilitate learning through filling out an exit slip.

Classroom Management Exit Slip Helpful Formative Data

An exit slip can take many forms, but ultimately it is a tool student's use to briefly report on their learning that day. This feedback is the last thing students do before they exit each day. Teachers receive this feedback from their students and have timely, formative data on their students' learning.

Like all formative data, exit slip can them be utilized by teachers to gain insight into student understanding plan accordingly for upcoming instruction. Exit slips help teachers answer that ultimate question. "What did students learn today?" It also helps teacher identify areas of strength or weakness in student understanding.

Lecture time is 45 minutes. So teacher goes through today lesson that is confused to the students. At the end of the lessons, how teacher knows if they've understood the lesson she discussed? If she doesn't have any form of formative feedback available, then all she really has are hunches or

ABSTRACT

This paper intends to use exit slip as an assessment tool in the classroom. Since students have been taught English as a second language, all students in the classroom cannot get full information according to their background knowledge. So teachers need to check their understanding of the materials. By using exit slip that is assessment tool, teachers can know their needs and weakness.

KEYWORDS: check, need, understanding, assess, comprehension.

INTRODUCTION

In Myanmar, there are over 40 students in the classroom. Each student has different ability and skill. Assessing student comprehension is one of teaching methods. After teachers had taught the lessons, all students did not get the information. May be some students can get concept and a few cannot. If teachers notice this, this is a sign that teachers need to re-teach. How do teachers know their needs? By using exit slip that is a useful tool in the classroom, teachers can check their comprehension and weakness.

How Can We Use Exit Slips to Facilitate Learning?

Preparing for a class includes planning the end of the lesson. Closure is as vital as the content and style of presenting a lesson because students tend to retain information better during the last few minutes of class.

feelings indicating what her students got out of her time together. If, however, she implements a simple form of formative such as exit slips-then she's got a much stronger indication of how well students grasped today's lesson concept and are ready for the next one.

Another important point to add about exit slips is that they don't just help the teacher. They help the students just as much. Exit slips provide an opportunity for students to reflect on their own learning. May be some students thought they understood the concept better than they really did, may be others didn't put that much thought into the learning at all. Regardless, their reflection will help reveal to them if they understood what they were supposed to or if further steps might be necessary for them to proactively grasp the content.

Integrating exit slips in class

Implementing the use of exit slips the classroom is quite easy. The teacher determines the question or the area in which they want information. The decided upon question can either be mentioned on index cards, or stated verbally, written on a list, or posted on a bulletin board. At the end of the class, collect these exit slips and review them. This information may then be used to plan your next class.

Exit slips are a great way to facilitate learning as students are encouraged to synthesize and organize the material in their own words while it is still fresh in their minds.

How to come up with good exit slip prompts?

Here are some example prompts to draw inspiration from:

1. Write down three things you learned today.

2. If you had to explain today's lesson to a friend, what would you tell him/her?
3. What question do you have about what we learned today?
4. What part of the lesson did you find most difficult?
5. What would you like me to go over again next lesson?
6. Write down two questions you would put in a quiz about today's lesson.
7. What are the main points we covered today?
8. Did the group activity contribute to your understanding of the topic? Why?
9. Read this problem ...What would be your first step in solving it?
10. I used app X extensively today. Was it helpful? Why or Why not?

A Favorite Formative Assessment: The Exit Slip

Robert Marzano, classroom researcher and education author, recently wrote in depth about this formative assessment. He shares four uses for exit slips. Students:

1. Rate their current understanding of new learning
2. Analyze and reflect on their efforts around the learning
3. Provide feedback to teachers on an instructional strategy
4. Provide feedback about the materials and teaching

An exit slip can also be a great way to set up the next day's learning. With that in mind, here's a few uses to consider:

1. Discover Shared Interests

Before introducing a group project that includes student choice, students can respond to a strategic question via an exit slip, sharing their primary topics of interest and their reasons.

2. Activate Prior Knowledge

Instead of taking time during class to create a concept/topic map, you can provide students with the concept or topic word at the end of the class, activating their prior knowledge, and have them write words and phrases related to it on their half sheet of paper. When they come into the classroom the next day, they will see all their ideas displayed around the main word or phrase. This brainstorm also serves as a diagnostic check for the teacher.

3. The Start of an Essay

The low-stakes nature and end-of-class urgency of the exit slips creates a space for students to write quickly, jotting

down all that they know about something. You could ask, for example, "Tell me all that you believe to be (a character's) motivation for ...in the book...". Students write and write for several minutes. You can hand it back to them the next day, telling them they have a start to their first draft of a character analysis essay.

4. Surveying Students

Use the exit slip to survey students on a current issue or hot button topic related to them. (i.e. curfew, cellphone use at school). The data can be used to launch a lesson on the art of debate, or start a unit on argumentative writing (75% of the class agrees that ...").

The beauty of the exit slip is that it puts the learning in the students' hands. It's also empowering for them when they see what they have shared influence what and how they are the next day.

Benefits of Exit Slips

Exit slips are beneficial for both students and teachers. They help the students reflect on the information they learned, process the concepts and express their thoughts on learning. Exit slips encourage students to summarize the lesson, identify key points, analyze critically and refine their knowledge and learning. Integrating exit slips as part of the lesson may assist students in developing better comprehension and in-depth processing of the lecture.

CONCLUSION

Teachers can use exit slips every lecture time. Exit slips provide teachers with an informal measure of how well students have understood a topic or lesson. But lecture time is 50 minutes. For Myanmar students, 5 minutes is not enough to answer short questions. Sometimes, it takes 10 minutes them to answer the questions. So, teachers need to use exit slips for difficult or confused lessons.

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